

Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) Technologies and Sustainable Development Goal 11 (Sustainable Cities & Communities) in South Africa

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This study examines the role of Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies in advancing Sustainable Development Goal 11 (SDG 11), which seeks to promote inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities and communities in South Africa. The purpose of the study is to explore how emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), big data analytics, and smart infrastructure can be leveraged to improve urban governance and service delivery within South African municipalities. A qualitative research approach was adopted, drawing on a systematic review of secondary data, including academic literature, government reports, and policy documents related to 4IR and urban development. The study also incorporates selected case examples from South African municipalities to illustrate practical applications of digital technologies in areas such as smart service delivery, urban planning, and infrastructure management. The findings reveal that 4IR technologies have significant potential to enhance municipal efficiency, transparency, and responsiveness. Digital platforms enable real-time monitoring of service delivery, improve data-driven decision-making, and foster citizen engagement. However, the study also identifies key challenges, including digital inequality, inadequate infrastructure, skills shortages, and institutional resistance to technological change, which may hinder effective implementation. The study concludes that while 4IR technologies present transformative opportunities for achieving SDG 11 in South Africa, their success depends on addressing structural and capacity-related constraints. The implications of the study suggest that policymakers and municipal leaders must invest in digital infrastructure, promote skills development, and establish enabling regulatory frameworks to ensure inclusive and sustainable urban transformation.

Keywords: 4IR technologies, sustainable urban development, sustainable development goal

The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) has emerged as a powerful force to remodel and transform urban economies into the digital age, which is marked by rapid technological advancements. To address several urban constraints brought on by rapid urban population increase, housing shortages, traffic congestion, and environmental degradation, global cities are utilizing the new era of creative solutions. Thus, sustainable urban development is required. In order to achieve SDG 11 in South Africa, this study intends to investigate the possible avenues suggested by 4IR technologies in transforming and shaping sustainable and smart cities. Additionally, the study investigates 4IR technologies, such as digital governance, the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), in achieving SDG 11.

This article starts by providing an insightful background to the study, followed by the problem statement and the urban challenges. This paper also identifies the key 4IR technologies driving sustainable urban development, and the comparative pathways of traditional versus 4IR-enabled urban development. In addition, this

article submits that the interconnection of technology and sustainable urban development methods enhances the urban inclusivity, climate resilience, economic growth and governance efficiency, as well as reliability of public transport. Consequently, this article ends by proposing a holistic framework for the integration of 4IR into the city's development infrastructure.

Background on the Development of 4IR Technologies

In the digital age linked to swift technological advancements, the 4IR has emerged as a powerful force for reshaping as well as transforming economies, societies, and industries across the world (Moll, 2022; Kud, 2023; Khoza, 2025). In this regard, world cities are implementing a new perspective of innovative solutions to address the complex problems posed by urban expansion, transport congestion, and environmental degradation (Rainnie & Dean, 2020). This therefore calls for an immediate need for sustainable development. In South African context, Johannesburg stands as the key economic center of the Southern African Development Community (SADC). This city shows a well-built urban area in Africa that is contending with the challenges of rapid urban population growth, housing shortages, traffic congestion, and environmental degradation while striving to enhance the quality of life for its diverse inhabitants via several fields of practice, like urban planning (Khoza, 2025).

Due to traffic jams and environmental harm, the prevalence of private automobiles has put major strain on cities like Johannesburg

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(Mbatha, 2025; Ndebele, 2018). Johannesburg has been encountering intensifying urban pressures, consisting of a fast-growing population. Many cities around the globe are at a crossroads and are calling for the adoption of 4IR technologies to pave the way for an urban mobility framework that is more efficient, sustainable, and ecologically conscious (Makazhe & Maramura, 2024; Risimati & Gumbo, 2018). Through the utilization of 4IR technologies and their integration into its transportation infrastructure, Johannesburg has started a remarkable journey towards becoming a smart, sustainable city. This indicates that the city has investigated opportunities to attain sustainable transportation, improve socioeconomic development, and lessen environmental impacts.

Since the Industrial Revolution began, technical innovations have been adopted. For instance, industries in the 20th century were driven by electricity, which led to an increase in production, whereas in the 19th century, industries were mostly powered by steam and water engines. Industries were automated in the 1970s (Hoosain, Paul, & Ramakrishna, 2020). We are currently living in the 4IR era, a wave that recognizes that cyber-physical systems may communicate with each other through the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and big data, among other means (Makazhe & Maramura, 2024). The 4IR is expected to foster productivity and enhance growth (Hoosain, Paul, & Ramakrishna, 2020; Manazir, 2023). In the 1980s, the United States introduced the Cyber-Physical System (CPS), while Japan introduced the Intelligent Manufacturing System (IMS) (Munir, Sadiq, Abbas, & Rasul, 2024). Germany recently embraced Industry 4.0, while China unveiled China Manufacturing 2025 (Jiyuan, Baicun, Liu, & Yuan, 2018). Digital technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, blockchain, robotics, and 3D technologies have therefore emerged as important tools and answers to a variety of global problems as we stand on the precipice of 4IR.

Furthermore, 4IR has evolved as a vital and transformative force changing the world. Its importance stems from the tremendous effects of its contemporary technologies, particularly those governed by internet connectivity, on our methods of learning, working, and living (Kibe, Kwanya, & Nyagowa, 2023; Via Afrika, 2020). The first three industrial revolutions are the focus of 4IR's strengths. For instance, people from earlier generations were only able to learn from written texts kept in libraries or other physical sources. The use of printed materials has been eclipsed by the introduction of 4IR. Chat Generative Pre-Training Transformer (ChatGPT) and other large language models (LLMs) are being used by contemporary students to assist with research and academic writing (Gordijn & Have, 2023). Therefore, putting forward-thinking plans into action is becoming more important as technological promotion develops at a rapid rate.

The operating procedures of people have been altered by the 4IR. This technical breakthrough has affected every economic area. However, nothing is known about how 4IR technologies are being used in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. In order to help South Africa achieve SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities & Communities), this research aims to investigate how 4IR technologies might be used to support sustainable urban development. Examining how technologies like IoT, AI, and big data can be used to improve housing, energy, and transportation systems in South African cities was one of the study's goals. It also investigates how 4IR technologies might minimize ecological footprints in urban settings

by optimizing resource management (energy, water, and waste). The article also looked at digital governance methods that promote accountability, transparency, and involvement in urban development. Finally, it pinpointed tactics that can be used to leverage 4IR technology for sustainable urban development in South Africa.

Review of Literature

The 4IR has emerged as a potent catalyst for changing and reforming economies, society, and businesses globally in the digital age characterized by constant technology breakthroughs (Moll, 2022). In this sense, cities around the world are adopting a fresh viewpoint of creative solutions to deal with the intricate problems that traditional urban development techniques have created, like a lack of housing, traffic jams, environmental damage, and the fast urban population expansion. Leaks, outages, and waste occurred because of traditional systems' emphasis on human monitoring of water, garbage, and power.

Traditional methods address issues after they arise rather than before they arise. According to Matimolane, Selane, and Mathivha (2024), traditional urban technologies in South Africa result in inefficiencies such as 3040 water losses and inconsistent electricity, with over 1000 hours of load-shedding in 2023. Only 64% of households have access to municipal garbage services, resulting in poor waste management in urban areas due to the adoption of traditional methods (Nyika, Onyari, Mishra, & Dinka, 2019). Sustainable development is therefore desperately needed. With an emphasis on accomplishing Sustainable Development Goal 11 (SDG 11) in South Africa, this article attempts to explore the possible avenues provided by 4IR technologies in the transformation and development of sustainable and smart cities. The study also explores the analysis of 4IR technologies, such as ITS, AI, IoT and digital governance. In light of this, the article aims to investigate how 4IR technologies can revolutionize the sustainable urban development of South African cities.

Theoretical Framework

The New Public Management (NPM) theory, which first surfaced in the 1980s and gained international recognition as a reaction to persistent inefficiencies and bureaucratic roadblocks in conventional public administration systems, serves as the theoretical foundation for this investigation (Legreid & Christensen, 2017). In order to increase the efficacy and efficiency of public services, this approach places a strong emphasis on ideas taken from private sector management techniques. NPM can provide useful insights and reform initiatives in the context of South Africa, which has struggled with issues like housing shortages, traffic congestion, rapid population increase, and environmental deterioration.

In light of this, it can be observed that NPM theory aids municipal leaders in utilizing 4IR technologies for sustainable urban development, which is a means of achieving SDG 11 in South Africa. Imperial (2021) claims that the NPM concentrates on establishing precise performance goals and holding public employees responsible for meeting them. South Africa has adopted 4IR technologies in a number of agencies in accordance with NPM principles. According to Frederiksen and Hansen (2017), the NPM promotes giving public employees the ability to make decisions based on local needs and goals and decentralizing decision-making authority to lower levels of government. This has inspired each city

in South Africa to be in charge of its urban development initiatives to achieve the broad goals of realising sustainable cities and communities. Strong administrative and leadership skills are crucial in the public sector. Innovative leaders who are able to use 4IR technologies for sustainable urban development have excellent managerial and leadership qualities. This demonstrates the NPM theory's applicability in this case since it enables municipal officials to use 4IR technologies for sustainable urban development, which is a means of achieving SDG 11 in South Africa.

Defining Concepts

Fourth Industrial Revolution Technologies: Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies refer to the current era characterised by the interconnectedness of digital, physical and biological systems (Schwab, 2016). This covers technological innovations such as blockchain technology, digital governance, AI, IoT, ML, robots, biotechnology, and ITS. This study is connected to 4IR technologies because they have become a force for changing and modifying industries, economies, and society worldwide.

Sustainable Urban Development: According to Oconnell (2023), sustainable urban development is the process linked to designing and managing urban development to meet the residents' needs, paying attention to not jeopardies the needs of future generations. This strategy strikes a balance between social advancement, environmental responsibility, and economic prosperity. The accomplishment of SDG 11, sustainable cities and communities is guaranteed by a sustainable urban development status. Sustainable cities are now considered smart cities because of the introduction of 4IR technologies.

Urban Challenges: The high cost of urban land is the main barrier to the construction of social housing. The implementation of affordable housing initiatives is hampered by the privatization of land and the rising market value of properties (Masters, 2021). While state-sponsored programs are hampered by the sluggish acquisition of prime land, urban developers usually concentrate on high-income housing since it is profitable (Turok, Rubin, & Scheba, 2024). Furthermore, attempts to remedy previous displacements through land restitution sometimes led to intricate legal issues that further delay housing construction. A major issue caused by the absence of an efficient expropriation procedure is the idle or contentious status of land parcels (Makalima & Sokhetye, 2025).

Additionally, investors buy land for possible future gains rather than for immediate development, which exacerbates the affordability situation (Wilcox, Haffner, Mota, & Elsinga, 2024). Because of this, the land that may be used for social housing is left idle or undeveloped. These delays are exacerbated by the regulatory obstacles involved in rezoning property for affordable housing; demand continuously outpaces supply, creating an inefficient loop (Makalima & Sokhetye, 2025). Furthermore, the lack of infrastructure in development zones discourages investment because developers bear most of the expense of improving roads, water, and power, making low-priced housing developments unfeasible. Additionally, urban growth frequently results in the loss of natural resources and environmental deterioration, including contamination of the air and water (Ferro, 2024; Quélin & Smadja, 2021). Therefore, 4IR powered sustainable urban development is essential to mitigating these issues and ensuring a secure environment for coming generations.

When it comes to the idea of smart cities, Geoffery West, a famous

physicist, is well-known. He predicted that in the next few years, cities would threaten the earth (West, 2017; Williams & Charles, 2024). This is because during the past 200 years, urban expansion has increased at an alarming rate (West, 2017). Urban growth does, however, provide several challenges. These challenges include harm to the environment due to high pollution levels, health problems, illnesses, financial difficulties in adhering to budgetary constraints, energy shortages to maintain mobility, traffic jams, and businesses and households (Charles & Williams, 2024). Therefore, finding a smart way to tackle these challenges is surely at the centre of the paradigm supporting smart cities as more of the globe is turning into urbanisation.

Key 4IR Technologies Driving Sustainable Urban Development

Having progressed from its infancy to a point that will transform conventional network infrastructures into a completely integrated future with the internet, the Internet of Things is regarded as the next big potential for the internet (Gubbi, Buyya, Marusic, & Palaniswami, 2013). This brings us to the idea of "smart homes," where a variety of electronic gadgets are connected to one another to provide high-quality interactive multimedia services in both directions (Al-Fuqaha et al., 2015). Thus, in order to achieve Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11, the goal of sustainable urban development can be realized through the use of 4IR technologies.

A substantial amount of data, referred to as Big Data, is produced in this setting where many devices communicate with one another (Hashem et al., 2015). Improved Big Data analytics can be crucial to the development of Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) and smart home technology (Chen, Mao, & Liu, 2014). This kind of Big Data analysis gives us a better grasp of Big Data and offers insightful information about future developments, plans, and improvements. A wide range of security and monitoring applications are supported by this technology, and it is critical for urban development to understand the need for service profiling to boost productivity and possibly improve city administration.

According to Moll (2022), the container that houses the gasoline for sustainable urban development is cloud computing. This is because cloud computing is affordable, scalable, elastic, dependable, secure, and accessible worldwide (Williams & Charles, 2024). As a result, this 4IR technology is important for mining, processing, and storing the massive volumes of big data required to create sustainable urban development. In order to achieve SDG 11 through effective citizen involvement, cloud computing is essential (Khoza, 2025). Furthermore, cloud computing can be used to improve the efficiency of important urban development sectors such as housing, electricity, water, and transportation (Mohamed et al., 2015). Thus, cloud computing is another 4IR technology that can be harnessed to achieve SDG 11 in South Africa.

We live on a technological marvel where computers continue to accelerate while the price of processing power continues to plummet. This is pushing for AI while encouraging the advancement of machine learning (ML), which is the capacity of computers to learn from data (Aoun, 2017). Additionally, AI technologies are a key 4IR technological enabler for future smart cities because they can perceive, learn, and simultaneously reason to boost people's and organizations' capabilities (Aoun, 2017; Schwab, 2016). Thus, 4IR-related AI and ML technologies can be used to promote sustainable

urban development. In order to improve data-driven decision-making, city authorities can diagnose problems and predict the necessary quantifiable steps by examining both historical and real-time data to find patterns (Choudhary, 2019; Schwab, 2016). Therefore, machine learning is another 4IR technology that South Africa may use to accomplish SDG 11.

The Integration of 4IR Technologies and Sustainable Urban Development

Moreover, the future smart cities may use AI to improve city services including waste collection, pedestrian and vehicle traffic management, energy usage, and parking availability, through a variety of algorithms in order to achieve SDG 11 (Schwab, 2016). However, being 'smart' goes beyond technology alone; it is about building livable, equitable, and sustainable urban spaces where 4IR technology largely acts as a catalyst for solutions to address urban problems like inequality, climate change, and resource depletion.

Robotics, intelligent automation, and drones represent some of the most rapidly advancing technologies of the 4IR. In the sustainable smart cities of the future, these technologies will set the standard for how we approach design, management, living, working, and interpersonal engagement in harmony with machines when they are integrated with the Internet of Things (IoT) (Khoza, 2025; Schwab, 2016). Furthermore, the McKinsey Global Institute (MGI) has confirmed that AI can work in tandem with complementary technologies like robotics to provide all-encompassing solutions. These include robotic surgery, autonomous driving, and household robots that can react to different stimuli (Woetzel et al., 2018).

The creation of robots with social and cognitive abilities is a key 4IR innovation relevant to sustainable urban development. These robots use Artificial Intelligence and speech recognition to converse with people in natural language. Along with exhibiting their own emotions, they may also identify and react to human emotions (Dubeldeman & Ward, 2020). Drones, robots, and intelligent automation are therefore crucial 4IR technologies that can be used to help South Africa achieve Sustainable Development Goal 11 (SDG 11).

Several studies have demonstrated that Eastern Cape municipalities are becoming smart municipalities, which are defined by the incorporation of digitization and the Internet of Things for urbanization and energy management (Batty, 2020; Masiba & Mphambukeli, 2023; Zindi, 2024). Additionally, a number of studies have used geographic information systems (GIS) multi-criteria decision analysis to determine suitable land locations for housing construction and the creation of smart cities across South Africa (Batty, 2021; Mukome, Seyam, & Amoo, 2022). These results make it clear that the establishment of a green node, which includes elements like digitalization, energy management, the Internet of Things, urbanization, and smart municipalities is crucial for the Eastern Cape's smart city growth. The GIS multi-criteria decision analysis is therefore urgently needed to identify appropriate land locations for the successful development of smart cities, which will ultimately result in the establishment of sustainable smart cities in South Africa.

The City of Johannesburg is undergoing a period of transformation as it works to develop into a world-class metropolis. To guarantee the city's operation, a variety of infrastructure has been put in place, and attempts are being made to improve the city by integrating 4IR technical breakthroughs (Mbatha, 2025). In order to

achieve the goal of making the city a smart city, it is crucial to make sure that the technological advances put in place are both useful and efficient for both citizens and service providers (Mukome et al., 2022). Urban planning is affected by a wide range of technologies, such as the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence, big data analytics, GIS, smart infrastructure, digital twins, autonomous vehicles, smart transportation, renewable energy, smart grids, digital platforms for citizen engagement, automation, and virtual and augmented reality. This might greatly enhance the City of Johannesburg's functionality and help it reach hitherto unheard-of heights (Mbatha, 2025). Technology integration is essential to urban innovation because it provides answers that conventional urban planning approaches frequently fall short of. In the end, technology might make the city more data-driven, improving its efficacy, efficiency, functionality, sustainability, and general quality of life for its citizens.

The support of infrastructure has been identified as a crucial element and constraint for the effective integration of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and the construction of Supply Chains (SC). This observation is supported by the focus on infrastructure in previous discussions, where factors relating to infrastructure were critical to a nation's overall potential for benefits and the primary drivers of difficulties (Ferro, 2024). Govender (2019) also supports this notion by describing how 4IR's success depends on overcoming infrastructure problems. He emphasizes the need for connectedness inside a nation and says that connective infrastructure is a fundamental requirement for the technological services of 4IR. Olaitan et al. (2021) mention that the evaluation of South Africa's preparedness for 4IR, which placed a strong focus on the nation's IT infrastructure, supports this claim even more. Although a country with more developed technology would be better equipped to implement 4IR, SA was found to have insufficient IT infrastructure (Olaitan et al., 2021). The research emphasizes the importance of infrastructure since Internet of Things applications require sophisticated support systems, such as reliable 5G mobile connections and energy supplies (Olaitan et al., 2021). This element is understood in the context of South Africa and its planning profession, which Govender (2019) identified as a crucial determining factor for the potential success of 4IR in the future.

Method

A qualitative semi-systematic literature review was adopted for the study with the aim of gaining an in-depth understanding of examines the role of Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies in advancing SDG 11. This paper reviewed current literature on the role of Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies to further understand how technologies can be utilized to achieve SDG 11. The focus is not on the number of articles written on a particular topic but rather on the content of existing debates in understanding of the role of Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies in advancing SDG11. This study used Scopus, Google Scholar, Sabinet, and Web of Science databases to search for relevant articles on the role of Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies in advancing SDG 11, ensuring comprehensive coverage.

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) approach was then used to search for articles. The use of PRISMA had several advantages that fitted the semi-systematic nature of this article. The study adopts the PRISMA framework to guide data collection because it offers a robust and

transparent method for conducting systematic literature reviews (Creswell & Poth, 2023).

Table 1

Article Retrieval Limits

Retrieval Limit	Explanation
Database	Scopus, Google Scholar; Sabinet, and Web of Science databases
Search field	Title, abstract, keywords
Keywords	“4IR Technologies AND SDG 11 in South Africa”
Open access	All
Years	2016-2025
Author names	Exclude unidentified names
Publication stage	All
Document Type	All
Affiliation	All
Country	South Africa
Source type	All
Language	English

Note. Researcher' Construction, 2026

As shown in Table 1, the search keywords were “4IR Technologies AND SDG 11 in South Africa”, In the initial search which used the first three principles in Table 400 articles were identified. However, when the last 8 principles were applied, 200 articles were eliminated to remain with 200 articles. This number was still considered large for qualitative study. The search was narrowed down to select articles that has the term “4IR Technologies AND SDG 11 in South Africa” in the title. This led to the exclusion of 130 articles to remain with 70 articles. The exclusion and inclusion criteria were then applied to determine whether they were in South Africa. An additional 30 articles were eliminated to remain 40 with articles.

The documents selected were then screened for inclusion in the study based on their titles and abstracts date of publication which were subsequently subjected to a full-text review to assess their relevance in the study. Documents that met the study's inclusion criteria were reviewed, and relevant information was extracted to support the presented arguments. Articles that used multi-case studies that included other countries outside South Africa were excluded. Furthermore, the author left out all the articles that could not be downloaded. These additional measures resulted in the elimination of 10 articles to remain with a sample of 30 which were then considered in the final analysis.

The selected articles were then subjected to content analysis whereby the presence of themes was determined from the sampled articles. This analysis was manually, with no computer software. Texts were read through to determine recurrent aspects in the texts.

Sustainable Urban Development through 4IR Technologies

Integration of 4IR Technologies into Urban Infrastructure

Based on the Schwab (2016) article, 4IR has the potential to boost levels of global income at the same time improving the population's life quality across the globe (Schwab, 2016). In support, Herweijer (2017) alluded that the 4IR carries great promise to fast-growing Cities in Africa and Asia to outshine traditional development while speeding-up the transition. According to this analysis, it can be noted

that South Africa's urban infrastructure has been up-to-date, and with the advent of 4IR technologies, citizens' quality of life can be improved through improved transportation, safer streets, green spaces, at the same time with increased economic opportunities.

The challenges related to city planning and management will become more complex and prominent as urbanization picks up speed and the world's population is expected to reach 10 billion by the end of this century, with more people wanting to live in urban areas (United Nations [UN], 2024). Technology integration will enable planners to create more potent solutions to the major problems brought about by mass urbanization. As a result, the Fourth Industrial Revolution's (4IR) technologies will play a critical role in helping city planners manage the various problems that arise in their urban settings. As a result, technology will be crucial to promoting sustainable urban growth in South Africa.

While integrating AI technology into urban settings presents opportunities for increased sustainability, efficiency, and quality of life, it also raises serious worries about possible drawbacks (Khoza, 2025). The potential for 4IR technologies to worsen already-existing social injustices is a significant criticism of their application (Arroub & Zahi, 2016). In South Africa, the application of AI-driven technology can unintentionally reinforce preexisting prejudices and discriminatory practices brought about by the apartheid era (Marr, 2022). This is demonstrated in domains such as employment practices, resource allocation, and predictive policing. Although there is potential for integrating 4IR and AI technology in urban environments, South Africa and urban planners must actively address the associated concerns. As a result, the combination of increasing urban migration, resource shortages due to swift population growth, the rise of advanced smart technologies, a transition towards people-centered environments (Mbatha, 2025). The growing focus on green and sustainable development in South Africa has led to an increased demand for sustainable urban development initiatives.

The IoT is considered the next major opportunity for the Internet, having evolved from its early stages and now entering a phase that will revolutionize traditional network infrastructure into a fully integrated future with the internet (Rai, Singh, & Kumar, 2023). As a result, this leads us to the concept of smart homes, where various electronic devices are interconnected, enabling high-quality two-way interactive multimedia services (Hassebo & Tealab, 2023). To advance smart home technology, NPM and enhanced analytics of Big Data can significantly contribute to the development of Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) (Cesario, 2023). Big Data technology is utilized to support a broad spectrum of security and monitoring applications, and for urban development, it is crucial to understand the demand for service profiling to enhance efficiency and potentially improve city management (Zhuang, Cenci, & Zhang, 2024). Therefore, in this context, this technology provides a deeper understanding and valuable insights into future developments in the South African urban sector, as well as planning and growth, thereby facilitating a clearer achievement of SDG 11 in South Africa.

Ultimately, the considerable potential of Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies is concentrated in four primary domains: (1) improved strategies for dynamic management of urban resources, (2) theoretical insights and knowledge acquisition concerning urban patterns and processes, (3) approaches for urban engagement and civic involvement, and (4) advancements in urban

management, planning, and policy evaluation (Thakuriah et al., 2017). For instance, a city in South Africa would utilize these technologies to collect real-time data to improve the quality of services offered to its residents. Prior to this era, commonly referred to as the age of the smart city (Batty, 2020) it was observed that computers were mainly employed to support planning activities, even though data and information had become essential to the operations of the routine planning system. This is particularly apparent in planning competencies, which are crucial for ensuring sustainable urban development, thereby achieving Sustainable Development Goal 11 in South Africa.

Enhancing Environmental Sustainability through Digital Innovation

In order to facilitate comprehensive simulation, analysis, and testing prior to real deployment, digital twins serve as virtual representations of physical assets, processes, or systems. Without requiring actual prototypes, companies can explore and improve their designs by developing a digital model, which reduces energy and material waste (Mazzetto, 2024). By reducing resource consumption, waste, and environmental effect, digital twins are crucial for promoting sustainability (Bibri, 2023). Professionals must be trained in modeling, data analysis, and predictive maintenance to develop green skills using digital twins (Mazzetto, 2024; Sharma et al., 2025). Thus, local governments are promoting sustainable urban development by incorporating digital twins into projects, enabling them to make decisions that align with SDG 11 and environmental objectives.

In order to support sustainable urban development, IoT technology is transforming resource management and oversight (Alam & Saini, 2023). The Internet of Things makes it easier to collect and analyze real-time data, which is crucial for environmental monitoring, by linking devices and sensors (Rai et al., 2023). Internet of Things can optimize waste collection routes, control building energy usage, and assess air quality, all of which contribute to a healthier urban environment in terms of sustainable urban growth. Data analysis, sensor technology, and systems integration are the competencies needed to interact with IoT in sustainability contexts (Cesario, 2023; Hassebo & Tealab, 2023). Thus, the study leads to the conclusion that municipal leaders with these abilities may deploy IoT systems that monitor and improve resource use, guaranteeing that water, electricity, and other resources are used as efficiently as possible to support sustainable urban development.

Although incorporating AI technology into urban environments has the potential to improve efficiency, sustainability, and quality of life (Bibri, 2023) there are serious worries about potential negative consequences. By improving energy efficiency and lowering carbon emissions in a variety of industries, artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionize sustainability initiatives (Kumar et al., 2022). Large datasets can be analyzed by AI algorithms to find patterns and forecast usage trends, allowing for more effective resource management (Zhang et al., 2021). AI-driven energy management systems may modify lighting, heating, and cooling in response to current occupancy and weather, cutting down on wasteful energy use and encouraging the development of clean, sustainable cities (Bibri & Allam, 2021; Mohanty et al., 2020). Urban sectors must therefore be skilled in data science, machine learning, and environmental analytics, all of which are essential for

attaining sustainable urban development to successfully apply AI for sustainability.

Promoting Inclusive Digital Governance and Citizen Participation

According to Bartoletti and Faccioli (2020), digital platforms are crucial in improving civic engagement because they allow people and groups to participate globally in addressing both individual and communal concerns. Citizens are empowered by innovative technologies and digital platforms, which promote public participation in group decision-making processes (Antonucci et al., 2022; Vlad et al., 2023). The public now has more opportunities to participate in governance, which has an impact on policymaking thanks to digital technologies. According to this analysis, technological advancements can result in the emergence of different terms in a variety of fields, such as civic tech, digital democracy, data governance, e-participation, and democratic innovation. These terms are all made possible by digital means (Aytac, 2024; Bayat & Kawalek, 2023; Royo et al., 2024). Currently operating in a variety of formats, these platforms encourage and improve public engagement, which helps accomplish SDG 11.

Through live streaming, a dashboard provides government departments with up-to-date statistics and information. The government can act quickly to support residents during any incident by using these digital platforms (Kitchin, 2014). The government must set up a dashboard to monitor the situation from the central control room in order to fulfill the goal of developing sustainable urban development. Real-time data, live streaming street photos, and interactive maps on dashboards are now provided to sustainable cities. The Dublin administration started using a dashboard to monitor the city in 2014; other municipalities across the world can learn from this concept (Kitchin, 2014; Kitchin, Maalsen, & McArdle, 2016). This platform's main goal is to enable real-time communication with citizens in order to promptly address their issues (Vlad et al., 2023). As a result, the dashboard approach plays a critical role in promoting inclusive digital government and citizen involvement, both of which are necessary for South Africa to achieve SDG 11.

A sophisticated technological breakthrough, Blockchain Technology (BCT) aims to guarantee the security and transparency of shared information, which is essential for achieving sustainable urban development status. In order to achieve SDG 11 in South Africa, BCT creates an independent, transparent, and decentralized information system. This is further corroborated by the assertion that using this system in government organizations gives users assurance that the data they keep is safe and unaltered (Aleisa, 2024; Briassoulis, 2021). Every participant (referred to as a node) has a copy of the ledger to record transactions, and the technology functions as a chain network in which all components have access to information.

The outstanding feature of this technology is that it removes the possibility of information leaking within the network, enabling people to share their information with government agencies with total security and safety guarantees. Thus, it can be said that by using BCT to achieve SDG 11, the South African government can efficiently collect and distribute information among all stakeholders.

Conclusion

Cities in South Africa are poised to adopt 4IR technologies to tackle

the intricate problems brought about by the country's fast urban population increase, housing scarcity, traffic jams, and environmental deterioration, as the paper mentioned above suggests. With an emphasis on accomplishing Sustainable Development Goal 11 (SDG 11) in South Africa, the article sought to explore the potential avenues provided by 4IR technologies in the transformation and growth of sustainable and smart cities. The New Public Management (NPM) served as the paper's compass. AI, IoT, e-governance, ITS, ML, blockchain, and dashboard systems are the main 4IR technologies that can be used to accomplish SDG 11.

These technologies have the potential to improve sustainability, efficiency, and quality of life, empower planners, improve techniques for dynamic management of urban resources, and increase public engagement. In order to achieve sustainable urban development, these 4IR technologies are essential. To guarantee greater responsibility, equity, and transparency in the use of AI in South African urban applications, the study urges the creation of national AI ethics and governance frameworks. Additionally, IoT sensors that enable real-time monitoring of waste collection trucks, energy grids, and water pipelines must be installed to enhance service delivery. Lastly, offering training programs for municipal employees focused on guaranteeing digital literacy and efficient use of e-governance technologies can help accomplish sustainable urban development and SDG 11. With this in hand, South Africa may accomplish SDG 11 by successfully advancing its sustainable development status.

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